

With or Without: Measuring Impacts of Books Metadata

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[Foreword](#)

[Introduction: Measuring Returns on Metadata Investments](#)

[Problem statement](#)

[Project overview](#)

[What we learned: Impacts on Scholarly User Experiences](#)

[Methodology](#)

[Results](#)

[Analysis](#)

[A Way Forward: Recommendations for Next Steps](#)

[Standards](#)

[Channels](#)

[Future research](#)

[Acknowledgements](#)

[References](#)

Foreword

By Jennifer Kemp, former Head of Partnerships at Crossref

In summer of 2021, Crossref issued an RFP for a wide-ranging project to explore the [‘Reach and effects of metadata.’](#) This effort was the culmination of a few years of internal and community discussions on ‘more and better’ metadata. It has long been taken as a given that metadata contributes to the discoverability of content and of course there is a body of existing research on it, though less than one might think. The research that exists is often niche, as research tends to be. For many in publishing and scholarly communications, it can be hard to extrapolate from narrowly scoped research on metadata to their own publishing programs.

So, the RFP was purposely broad and exploratory, a first step toward investigating big questions like what exactly is quality metadata? Is it simply free from error? Some of it, like dates that may seem straightforward, is open to interpretation. As someone who worked closely with users of the metadata, I always make the point that what’s in the metadata (and

what's not) matters so much because it is so widely distributed to such a variety of individuals, institutions, and machines that read the metadata. Not all of those connections are direct and some overlap, since many users rely on multiple sources of metadata. Even scoping the projects would take close collaboration.

Two complementary projects started in the fall of 2021, one focused on journals and the other, this research, on books, an area to which I am admittedly partial. There is a lot of scholarly book content not registered with Crossref, either at the book level (professional medical titles for one known example), and even more at the chapter level. The scope of this study purposely covers a broad range of disciplines and business models so there is something in it for everyone involved directly or indirectly with scholarly books.

Over the past 18 months, Lettie, Michelle, and I spent many hours discussing book publishing, discoverability, Google Scholar, and the metadata supply chain. I am grateful for the time and considerable energy they put into the research, a first-of-its-kind exploration of book discoverability in Google Scholar. This whole effort has been a highlight of my time at Crossref and I am thrilled that the results are being shared with the community. Crossref and I look forward to the discussions and future research this report will inspire.

Introduction: Measuring Returns on Metadata Investments

Metadata is more important than ever for information and content providers, playing a critical role in digital transformations, machine learning, collaborations, accessibility, analytics, and more. But, for all the discussion in our industry about metadata for scholarly communications, we lack a shared framework for assessing its impact on commercial goals, users' experiences, and other objectives. This project was inspired by Crossref's call to take up independent research that explores how new methods or metrics could assess metadata performance and its value to information users. With our interest in academic books and a passion for the information experiences of today's learners, scholars, and authors, we designed this project to illuminate the discoverability of books with and without DOIs in Google Scholar.

Problem statement

Why books? While metadata for journals receives much of our industry's attention, metadata for scholarly books is likewise key for discoverability, sales, and reader engagement, as well as forming a foundation for content and usage analytics. Publishers invest heavily in metadata for their content and the demand for book metadata is particularly high due to many publishers' multi-channel sales strategies for monographs, reference volumes, and other types of books. However, the publishing industry lacks shared benchmarks for assessing the value or impact of metadata on these commercial interests. We also foresee increasing attention on book metadata in our industry, because of research funder mandates for open-access publishing models (e.g., [OSTP](#) & [UKRI](#)), which increasingly include requirements for book and chapter metadata, as well as the growing number of [OA books being published](#).

Why Google Scholar? While Google Scholar began primarily as an index of journal articles, and their search index still favors the serial publishing model, their inclusion of scholarly books has been steadily on the rise. [Google Scholar](#) is a popular information-seeking starting point for researchers, learners, and other readers of scholarly content.

Why focus on the user journey? The information user journey and search experience were central to the design of this study. We believe the foundational purpose of metadata is to serve reader needs and scholarly practices. Therefore, this study measured the discoverability and usability performance of book metadata in the mainstream web, namely Google Scholar.

Project overview

As the first systematic review of how metadata impacts the discoverability of books in Google Scholar, this mixed-methods study employed a unique framework for scoring known-item queries and ranking metadata attributes by their impact on finding the target book or chapter. We tested books with and without title- and/or chapter-level DOIs in order to assess their impact on discoverability in Google Scholar. We selected a wide range of titles that represented

common types of books from various disciplines and providers, published under both traditional and open-access licenses.

This study found that books with DOIs are more readily discovered, despite Google Scholar's claim that their search index does not draw on DOIs or related metadata. We believe there is an indirect relationship at play, where books with DOIs benefit from the structured, open metadata associated with those DOIs -- which are used by hundreds of platforms and services, therefore distributed throughout the mainstream web and through standard publishing supply chains. Other factors, such as indexing partnerships directly with Google Scholar and Google Books, were found to be of equal or greater impact on books' discoverability. This report summarizes the design and outcomes of the study, concluding with recommendations for metadata strategy, industry initiatives, and future lines of inquiry.

What We Learned: Impacts on Scholarly User Experiences

Methodology

This mixed-methods study was designed to evaluate how the user experience is affected by the metadata for scholarly books in Google Scholar. This study is designed to measure the impacts and benefits of metadata for readers searching the mainstream web. Our research question was: *Are books with DOIs and associated metadata more easily found in Google Scholar than those without such metadata? What can we observe in Google Scholar that might indicate which metadata attributes contribute to highly discoverable books? Are book chapters readily found in Google Scholar and, if so, are they linked to the full title?*

Given its popularity with a range of stakeholders, this project measured metadata and its role in the discoverability of books in Google Scholar. We rated the search performance of more than 100 scholarly books indexed in Crossref. They consisted of monographs, reference works, and edited collections. They represent a range of disciplines, publishing models (open access, subscription, etc.), and sizes of publishers (see Table 1). We also conducted a supply chain analysis for each of the books tested, which assessed how high-value book metadata attributes are presented on publisher websites and in related services, such as reference managers.

For each publisher, we generated book lists tracking the following attributes:

- DOIs, if available, either at the title and/or chapter levels
- License types
- Publication type/format
- Title and subtitle
- Publisher (classified as either university, society, or commercial presses)

Table 1: Books tested in this study were provided by the following publishers

1. The American Chemical Society
2. American Mathematical Society
3. The American Society of Civil Engineers
4. Bloomsbury
5. Brill
6. De Gruyter
7. IOP Publishing
8. The IET (Institute of Engineering and Technology)
9. Karger Publishers
10. Open Book Publishers
11. Open Research Library
12. Princeton University Press
13. Routledge
14. Sage Publications Inc.
15. Thomas Telford Publishing
16. The University of California Press
17. The University of Edinburgh Press
18. The University of Michigan Press
19. World Scientific

This study drew on both qualitative and quantitative methods to simulate scholarly users' search and information experiences by executing more than 250 known-item queries and conducting heuristic analysis of metadata attributes found in search results. We established six query formulas (Table 2) and rotated these queries equally across the chosen books from each publisher.

Table 2: Formulas used to construct test queries

a.	Author/editor surname + 1-3 key terms (from the title, subtitle, or field of study)
b.	Author/editor surname + "book" + publication date
c.	Author/editor surname + "book" + publisher name
d.	Author/editor surname + "book" + area of expertise/field of study
e.	1-3 key terms (from the title, subtitle, and/or field of study) + "book"
f.	Full title (no subtitle) + "book"

We then rated each book's search results on a 5-point scoring rubric (Table 3) designed to measure the degree of friction in the user experience of locating the book in question. In this project, we defined user experience friction as the number of clicks required to locate the target book; the higher the score, the fewer the clicks and, correlatively, the better discoverability. We then ranked metadata attributes by their impact on search performance scores. This unique method was developed based on our own original research into academic user experiences and scholarly information practices, as well as a review of relevant literature (see [references](#) below).

Table 3: Search result scoring rubric	
Clicks	Score
0	5
1	4
2	3
3	2
4	1
5	0

The supply-chain tests consisted of 2 books per publisher (34% of the sample set). We reviewed the presentation of DOIs and book-type attributes in other mainstream tools and platforms, specifically on consumer ebook platforms (Google Play and Amazon) and third-party indices (Zotero and ResearchGate). Library sales/management systems, link resolver databases, and library discovery services were deemed out of scope for this project, given our focus on openly available book indices.

While this is the first systematic review of book metadata in Google Scholar, we recognize the limitations of this research. We analyzed books with and without title- and/or chapter-level DOIs, but did not endeavor to test discoverability performance before and after the addition of DOI metadata. Taking up such an approach would be an excellent area for future research.

While we took care to test books across all major fields of study, the project scope is limited to books with chapters, as opposed to books with subsections, serials, multimedia, or other types of content. The scope was also limited to books published in English during the last 10 years. We selected books using the Crossref API and focused on the performance of attributes included in DOI metadata, which excludes abstracts, keywords, and a controlled taxonomy of book types.

This project was also limited to the analysis of metadata as it appears in Google Scholar, which is a specialty database provided by a large commercial organization, therefore we cannot control for personalization features and search algorithms that impact page rank, indexing accuracy, etc. This scope also limited our testing to Google Scholar and did not extend to Google Books, library discovery services, or other search engines.

Results

The results generated by this study indicate that users experience less friction when searching for books with one or more DOIs and more friction when books do not have DOIs. Test scores reveal higher discoverability scores (less friction) for books with DOIs assigned at the title level (4.8 / 5) and/or chapter level (4.4 / 5) than those without any DOIs (3.2 / 5). Some of the top-performing books had title-level DOIs, but not chapter DOIs; whereas, books with both title and chapter DOIs did not perform measurably better than those with only title-level DOIs.

Discoverability was not significantly impacted by the type of book and we tracked variations by license, format, and topic.

- License: Books published under an open-access license performed only slightly better (4.5 / 5) than those published in traditional models (4.2 / 5), in part because we found that OA books had many more access points in the Google Scholar index.
- Format: Edited and authored books performed the same (4 / 5) at both the book and chapter levels, despite Google Scholar's stated preference to index edited volumes.
- Topic: Books in humanities and social science disciplines performed better (4.2 / 5) than titles in scientific, technical, or medical fields (3.4 / 5), despite what we found to be Google Scholar's market focus on STM research and publishing practices.

When we ranked the performance of specific metadata attributes, we learned that high-value fields include the primary title paired with subtitles, author/editor surnames and/or field of study. Queries using the full book title performed best across the board and surfaced results for both the full title as well as specific chapters. However, queries using chapter titles produced variable results, most often surfacing results for the entire book; chapters were most easily found for titles that were also indexed in Google Books. Test queries using author/editor surnames paired with publisher names were the lowest performing overall. We also found that the use of publication dates in test queries was less effective than filtering results by publication date.

In the supply-chain analysis, we learned that DOIs and key metadata, such as book types, were inconsistently represented in related mainstream tools and services. Among the titles tested, using publisher websites as the citation target, 59% of book records imported to Zotero captured book and/or chapter DOIs. Titles were correctly indexed as books 53% of the time but defaulted to "webpage" 41% of the time. No DOIs were found in Research Gate records, most of which correctly indicated the titles as books. Not surprisingly, DOIs were not found in either Google Play or Amazon book records.

In our evaluation of Google Scholar search results, we found that items with the [Book] tag are usually privileged in rank and provide the most accurate citations, often only missing the city attribute in the citation. We learned that the [Book] tag indicates where Google Scholar can confidently identify an item as a book, which is due to the inclusion of that title in Google Books and/or a direct indexing relationship with Google Scholar. We did not find a measurable difference in performance for books based on platform hosting format, however, the lowest

performing books were also found to have limited metadata on the publisher sites, often missing details such as DOI and book type.

Based on these results, we found that ***book DOIs have an indirect impact on discoverability in Google Scholar***, however, they do not determine better access to the full text. Publishers who have already invested in Crossref data deposits generally perform better in Google Scholar than those who do not assign DOIs via Crossref or other registries. From this, we conclude that books with DOIs have “seeded” metadata throughout platforms/services, which Scholar may then draw on for indexing, linking, and ranking.

Analysis

To better understand and contextualize the results of this study, we reviewed our findings with a number of stakeholders, including Crossref, Google Scholar, and participating publishers. Three primary conclusions were drawn from this research, all of which reflect a disconnect between scholarly metadata standards and infrastructure, and their impact on open-web discoverability.

1. DOIs are important, but they are not enough to impact discoverability in the mainstream, open web.

The findings of this study demonstrate that, when it comes to optimizing metadata architecture and distribution for book publishing, DOIs have an indirect impact on discoverability, but must work in conjunction with other data standards and channels. DOIs and related metadata will have the greatest impact on search experiences in the mainstream web when they are applied diligently and robustly in all book publishing programs.

For Google Scholar, publishers’ commercial websites are considered the primary source of truth and should therefore present all relevant identifiers, including DOIs and related metadata. Equally, that metadata should align with Google Book records, which should ideally come from the primary publisher. As a rule, basic principles of search engine optimization (SEO) apply to Google Scholar and should be incorporated into publishers’ data and information standards.

2. Book and chapter types are diverse, ambiguous, and hard to categorize.

The scholarly publishing community has the opportunity to vastly expand the impact of DOIs and related metadata on open-web discoverability by normalizing book-type and chapter metadata standards. For example, when assigning a new book DOI, Crossref provides a field for indicating the type of book, however, it is an uncontrolled attribute (at the time of this writing).

Given the wide variation of book formats, the scholarly industry has not established a shared framework for book-type categories, therefore a majority of books registered with Crossref are classified as “other.” Google Scholar could draw book- and chapter-type indicators from DOI feeds for more accurate indexing if they were assured of accuracy

and consistently derived by a standardized framework for book-type and book-section categories.

3. Scholarly metadata standards have a limited impact on open-web discoverability and users' search experiences.

The data and information standards developed by the scholarly community, like DOIs, are limited in their ability to influence visibility and usage via the mainstream web. This study demonstrates that Google Scholar operates outside our established scholarly information infrastructure, instead favoring SEO and retail-oriented standards. This fact is important for publishers to keep in mind when adapting channel-based strategies for book production, marketing, and distribution.

A Way Forward: Recommendations for Next Steps

Standards

To harness more precise, granular discoverability of scholarly books and chapters in Google Scholar, the scholarly publishing industry would benefit from standardized approaches to disambiguating types of books and sections, parts, or chapters. Publishers could further leverage these standards to drive enhanced content and usage analytics, e.g., more accurate COUNTER reporting.

Types of books are not a controlled attribute recommended by the [NISO ebook metadata committee](#). Book-type attributes are also not normalized in DOI metadata, nor are there any existing classifications for book types in ONIX, BISAC, or ISBN standards. Achieving industry consensus on a book-type metadata framework would require forming a cross-organizational group to address the prevailing needs of scholarly book publishers, which we recognize could be a challenge, given the wide variety of books published by scholarly content providers.

Channels

The findings of this study, among others, prove that providers are best served when they construct and distribute metadata for scholarly publications based on the idiosyncrasies of key channels for information seeking and access. Adopting an operational understanding of search and reading experiences is critical for ensuring content is made available in the right format, and in the relevant platforms and services. While DOIs and related metadata were found to have an indirect impact on discoverability in Google Scholar, they are critical metadata assets when indexing content within the tools and databases commonly licensed for institutional usage, such as link resolvers and discovery services.

Future research

The outcomes from this project point to a number of valuable directions for future research into the impact of scholarly metadata on information experiences. In particular, further analysis is needed to understand how book chapters are handled in other channels of information seeking and other metadata standards (such as ISBNs). This same study could be easily replicated in other venues, such as those used for institutional subscriptions, such as by an academic library. These same methods could be adapted to evaluate the impact of metadata on the experiences of other types of users, such as those in clinical or corporate settings.

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